

Model inter-comparison for global high-resolution simulations

Deliverable D1.2

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Title image:

A snapshot of the models taken from the perspective of the Himawari 8 satellite. The images are for the cloud scene on 4 August 2016 and are qualitatively rendered based on each model's condensate fields to illustrate the variety of convective structures resolved by the models and the difficulty of distinguishing them from actual observations. From left to right: IFS-4 km, IFS-9 km, and NICAM (top row); ARPEGE, Himawari, and ICON (second row); FV3, GEOS5, and UKMO (third row); and SAM and MPAS (bottom row). Courtesy of Niklas Röber. See Stevens et al. (2019) for more details.

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1 Abstract /publishable summary

The DYAMOND project (**DY**namics of the **A**tmospheric general circulation **M**odeled **O**n Non-hydrostatic **D**omains) is the first initiative for a model intercomparison of global storm resolving (km-scale) climate simulations. The analysis of these simulations helps advancing our understanding of the climate system and improving the next-generation of weather and climate models. At the same time, it forces us to optimise workflow for the processing of the huge amounts of data generated by the upcoming generation of storm resolving global models. ESiWACE supports the DYAMOND project by providing and developing infrastructures for production-mode configurations. As the community of DYAMOND includes partners outside the ESiWACE project, the DYAMOND website serves as a platform for sharing and comparing climate and weather models at highest-resolution. It provides specific information for participants of the intercomparison project but also general information for a broader audience. For an easy participation in the initiative, ESiWACE provides input data on the website. For provision and inter-comparison of of these high resolution data, ESiWACE supports the DYAMOND initiative with with storage and computing time resources of the Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (DKRZ). For the current DYAMOND phase two limited disk space impels us to develop an attractive data library with a central point for data access. The ESiWACE DYAMOND team is closely involved in the discussions relating to the new hierarchical storage management and data workflow at DKRZ and contributes its unique experience in dealing with the output of storm-resolving simulations.

2 Conclusion & Results

ESiWACE2 supports the DYAMOND intercomparison initiative by providing

- an infrastructure for the provision of high-resolution data
- compute time and software for server-side processing of the high-resolution data
- support and guidance for processing of the high-resolution data
- a website documenting this infrastructure, incorporated into the ESiWACE portal
- easily accessible input data

For a smooth and convenient provision of data sets, a data library, called "Dyamond data library", has been developed. The provision of the DYAMOND data enables research by currently 58 users (32% women) from 29 institutions from Europe, North America and Asia. Due to dissemination activities like the data analysis competition within the Global Energy and Water Exchanges (GEWEX) project, specialised sessions at the EGU 2021 and the special edition on DYAMOND, published by the "Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan" the number of users will grow further.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	X
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	-
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	X
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	X
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	X
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	-

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

With the growth of supercomputer capacities, it is now becoming possible to perform storm resolving (km-scale) simulations of the global atmosphere. While regional simulations at storm resolving resolution have proven valuable for weather (Termonia et al., 2018) and climate simulations (Berthou et al., 2020), so far computational costs have been prohibitive for global set-ups. The DYAMOND simulations for the first time allow the study of interaction of the vertical energy transport in convective storm systems with the global-scale circulation, thus providing an unprecedented opportunity for the study of climatic extreme events and their future evolution in a changing climate.

As analytical solutions for *the whole climate system* do not exist, model intercomparisons, such as the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP)¹, have proven essential for assessing climate models and analysing features of modeled climates and the interactions characterising the climate system. The DYAMOND initiative (Stevens et al., 2019) takes the challenge to, for the first time, perform a model intercomparison of global, storm-resolving simulations. Never before have two global, storm resolving models been run for the same analysis period. In the first phase, nine models participated in the intercomparison, and we were overwhelmed by the success of the initiative. As the DYAMOND intercomparison is in its first iterations, it takes an agile approach, refining its strategy as things evolve. This is very different from the routined and very strict organisation of CMIP.

In a first phase, a period of 40 days from 1st of August 2016 was simulated, with all models starting from the same initial conditions. The resulting output data is called "DYAMOND Summer" data. Now in the

¹<https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip>

second, currently ongoing phase "DYAMOND Winter", the participating models simulate 40 days starting on the 20th of January 2020, also covering the EUREC⁴A field experiment (Bony et al., 2017; Stevens et al., (submitted)). The analysis of these simulations helps identifying robust features common to all models, and provides insights into implementation-dependence of the results (e. g. Arnold et al., 2020; Dueben et al., 2020; Stevens et al., 2020; Wedi et al., 2020). It thus simultaneously helps advancing our understanding of the climate system and improving the next-generation weather and climate models.

Within ESiWACE2², the DYAMOND initiative is supported within the scope of task 1.1. "Develop infrastructure for production-mode configurations". For this purpose ESiWACE2 provides

- an infrastructure for the use and provision of high-resolution data
- input data and scripts, which are necessary for contributing model data to the initiative
- a corresponding website, incorporated into the ESiWACE portal.

In this context, the DYAMOND website serves as a starting point of an infrastructure for sharing and comparing ESiWACE models at highest resolution. One central point of the infrastructure is the "DYAMOND data library" developed in the framework of this deliverable and hosted by DKRZ. In the following, these three parts are described in detail.

4.1 The DYAMOND website

The website of the DYAMOND initiative is part of the ESiWACE website <https://www.esiwace.eu> and can be found under the tab "Services". Its aim is to provide information for a broader audience as well as for participants of the intercomparison project. General information for a non-scientific audience is provided directly on the website, while more technical details for DYAMOND participants and contributors are provided as pdf documents or via links.

For a good overview, the first page³ provides a general description of the project as well as current news from the DYAMOND initiative. Here, also results of the initiative are published, like the review article by Stevens et al. (2019) or the special edition on DYAMOND, published by the "Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan" (JMSJ, 2020).

For each phase, a separate page is set up⁴, which provides more detailed information grouped into "Getting the data" and "Contributing to the project". Modelling groups that would like to contribute to the DYAMOND initiative with data sets can find the following information:

- a pdf document with the experiment protocol⁵ presenting the guidelines for participating modelling groups
- initial data (links for downloading), see subsection 4.2
- manuals of recommended tools (links) to process the initial data for individual needs.

To ease the participation in this intercomparison project, the protocol only requires a minimal amount of standardisation and metadata. For the output no explicit file format is prescribed. However, the community typically sticks to variations of the standard grib or NetCDF file formats. The Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M) has extended the Climate Data Operators (CDO) to work with these data sets, and, where necessary, model teams have provided sample codes for the processing of their data. To provide guidance

²**Please note:** *This report is about the work on this intercomparison performed in the context of the project ESiWACE2. ESiWACE2 is a direct follow-up of the project ESiWACE that ended in 2019 and already supported the intercomparison. We have established ESiWACE as a brand for both projects and have not changed the logo. Consequently, in this text, we use ESiWACE to denote the overall support activities and ESiWACE2 for aspects specific to the ESiWACE2 funding phase.*

³<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/dyiamond>

⁴<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/dyiamond/summer> and <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/dyiamond/winter>

⁵Satoh et al. (2017) and Klocke et al. (2019)

for the structuring of the DYAMOND Winter data sets, also a DYAMOND Winter Data request is provided on the web page of the second phase (see subsection 4.3). It contains suggestions for a file convention for the output data as well as an example from the ICON model.

Under "Getting the data", interested scientists can find an e-mail address to contact the DYAMOND coordination team via diamond@esiwace.eu. More information on how to get a DKRZ account, access and use the DYAMOND data library as well as some example scripts for post-processing will be provided via e-mail. For the already conducted DYAMOND Summer phase, also descriptions of participating models including a contact person for each model are given. This allows participants to find model-specific information and contacts to experts. Equivalent information will also be provided for the second phase as soon as corresponding data sets will be available in the library.

4.2 Input for models

Initial- and boundary conditions for the DYAMOND Winter simulations were provided by MPI-M in IFS grib and in NetCDF format. These files are shared via the DKRZ swift browser⁶, and the original request to the MARS database⁷ at ECMWF is provided on the web page for reference. This allows modelling groups to download the initial data set without generating an account and thereby to easily participate in the DYAMOND initiative.

4.3 Infrastructure for provision and use of high-resolution data

ESiWACE supports the DYAMOND simulations with in-kind resources of DKRZ and with resources obtained by applying in the bi-annual calls for the federal share of the DKRZ supercomputer. This allows ESiWACE to support the DYAMOND initiative with space on disk and HPSS tape archive for the provision of the high-resolution data as well as with compute time for post-processing and intercomparison of the model data sets. Furthermore, ESiWACE has obtained resources for joint MPI-M/DKRZ ICON simulations for the intercomparison.

Disk space, in particular in a super computing environment, is an expensive and limited resource. Even if DKRZ managed to keep most data of the first phase on disk, for the second and potential follow-up phases or initiatives, not all data can be made available for quick access at the same time. Therefore, the entire DYAMOND Summer and Winter data will be moved to tape and only parts of it will be provided on disk according to user requests. For a smooth operation of the DYAMOND Winter data collection and provision despite limited disk space, contributors are asked to adhere to a DYAMOND Winter Data request (a pdf document can be found on the webpage⁸) for file splitting and grouping of variables. With this request, we aim to

1. keep the total number of files limited so that handling is less cumbersome
2. keep files small enough for quick transfer and selective download from the tape archive
3. group variables where file sizes stay reasonable for the use in post-processing tools where loading from different files at the same time is cumbersome.

So a rather fine-grained data download will be possible.

4.3.1 the "DYAMOND data library"

The DYAMOND Summer intercomparison simulations have yielded more than one Petabyte of data, and we are expecting roughly two PB of data from the DYAMOND Winter experiments. DKRZ is making this data

⁶<https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/swift/swiftbrowser>

⁷<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/archive-datasets>

⁸<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/diamond/DYAMONDWinterDatarequestdetailsofficial.pdf>

available to any scientist interested in analysing. This service is provided via DKRZ's Mistral supercomputer and the associated hierarchical storage management (HSM) tape system. Any scientist can request access to these systems by sending an e-mail to diamond@esiwace.eu. To provide smooth operations and data fetching from the tape system, a set of scripts for use on the supercomputer have been developed. We have based the design of these scripts on the experiences we have made in the first phase of the DYAMOND intercomparison. The main practical observations were:

- Due to the unexpectedly good response to the project, the collected data sets had a total amount of roughly 1000 TB, which is too big for providing permanent disk access.
- While some data sets are in high demand, others are requested on an occasional basis only.
- Some users need one variable across all time slices, others need many variables for one time slice, so only a fine-grained splitting of data files allows for targeted provision of the necessary data on disk without massive overhead.
- Post-processed data by users tends to accumulate over time.
- Cleaning disk space from users' post-processed data is very difficult, as we do not want to interfere with their analysis, and users tend to need data access until their publication has passed the peer review process.

Based on these observations, we have decided to develop the "DYAMOND data library" at DKRZ as an attractive central point for data access. Users are requested to use data sets from within this library for their post-processing. While data sets in the library are available for all DYAMOND users, no write access is granted inside the library itself to avoid accidental data manipulation or data loss. By providing one convenient central repository, we aim at reducing the number of duplicate copies of the data sets on disk. In addition to the central raw data repository, we provide users with disk space for their analysis in a different directory. In combination with compute time for post-processing jobs and the user-friendly jupyter web service⁹, this allows for server-side processing and minimises the need for data transfer to the users' facilities.

To generate a user-attractive library we strive for designing a clear arrangement of the library. This is ensured by a central point of access, containing summer and winter data, example post-processing scripts, a library README file, index files to search for new data sets and a folder for data requests. The library README file explains to the user how to search for the required data sets in the archive using the 'listems' tool, a part of the 'packems' package (Wieners and Heydebreck, 2020). It also gives instructions on how to generate a request for these data by writing a simple text file. In addition, it describes where to find the downloaded data as well as first example post-processing scripts. These mechanisms are meant to make the DYAMOND data library easy to use. For illustration, the README file is given in the appendix A. For the second phase, we also aim to provide meta data of archived files in order to allow the user to find requested variables more easily. Provision of these meta data will depend on the structure of the future Winter data sets. The central e-mail address diamond@esiwace.eu and automated scripts for request processing ensure a fast response of the coordination team to the users. For more specific questions, users can, find a detailed description for each model and information of contact to experts on the DYAMOND web page.

Beside attractiveness for users, easy data archiving and request managing ensures a smooth operation of the data library. For archiving data sets, the 'packems' tools are used. These tools have been developed by MPI-M and DKRZ and allow an easy data handling and transfer between disk space and tape archive at DKRZ. Also the entire DYAMOND summer data, which had already been archived to tapes in the hierarchical HSM system, has been injected into the mechanics of 'packems', so that the download of the data is much easier now. This work was supported by Daniel Heydebreck (DKRZ) and Karl-Hermann Wieners (MPI-M). For sustainable archiving of the DYAMOND winter data sets, we are requesting users to split the data by

⁹<https://jupyterhub.dkrz.de>

time and kind, so a rather fine-grained downloading of data will be possible. In addition, we will try to further reduce the data memory size and extract meta data, but this will depend on the incoming datasets. For a fast reaction to user requests, e.g. requests for data, new participants, new contributors and data set archiving, a clear workflow with mainly automated processes has been developed and will be further adapted to actual needs. This ensures an easy distribution of work among the DYAMOND coordination team. Last but not least, a data access management has been designed to avoid a data pile-up by users, which would have to be cleaned by the DYAMOND coordination team.

5 References

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Wedi, Nils P., Inna Polichtchouk, Peter Dueben, Valentine G. Anantharaj, Peter Bauer, Souhail Boussetta, Philip Browne, Willem Deconinck, Wayne Gaudin, Ioan Hadade and et al., **2020**. A baseline for global weather and climate simulations at 1 km resolution. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 12(11):e2020MS002192. doi:10.1029/2020MS002192. e2020MS002192 10.1029/2020MS002192.

Wieners, Karl-Hermann and Daniel **Heydebreck**. *Pack'em ESMs! Tools for (un-)archiving Earth system model data*, **2020**. <https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/esmenv/wiki/Packems>.

6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Limited disk space for the DYAMOND Winter phase impels us to develop an attractive data library with a central point for data access.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

One aim of the European strategy for HPC is to enable research and innovation activities to make use of future exascale systems (EC Unit C.2, 2020). Numerical weather and climate models running on these systems will output huge data sets. By supporting a model inter-comparison for global high-resolution, ESiWACE2 improves the tool chain to manage data from climate and weather simulations. This enable the community to work with these data sets. Fostering climate and weather simulation groups to participate in the high-resolution inter-comparison DYAMOND boosts the European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing and future supercomputers.

8 Sustainability

To support participants of the initiative and gather outcomes from a wider community, ESiWACE2 is planning to organise a 3rd DYAMOND Hackathon in 2021.

For the sustainability of the DYAMOND data library, the ESiWACE DYAMOND team is closely involved in the discussions relating to the new hierarchical storage management (HSM) system and data workflow at DKRZ. This new storage system is designed by the company Cristie Data and will contain a metadata-driven workflow engine from StrongBox Data Solutions (SBDS) ¹⁰. Within the discussion about user requirements, ESiWACE contributes its unique experience in dealing with the output of storm-resolving simulations.

¹⁰DKRZ press release: <https://www.dkrz.de/communication/news-archive/en-neues-hsm>

8.1 Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

Since the second phase of DYAMOND is just starting, we rely on practical observations made during the first phase, see section 4.3.1.

8.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The DYAMOND simulations will be used as example workload of model output for the work in WP4. In WP5, DKRZ is extending the capabilities of visualisation tool Paraview for the reading of a larger variety of (ir)regular grids. This eases the analysis of the different models participating in the DYAMOND intercomparison on their native grids. As a first step, basic support for ECMWF's IFS has been implemented.

9 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

To encourage the use of the DYAMOND data by a wide community, ESiWACE is co-sponsoring a data analysis competition in the context of the "Global Atmospheric System Studies" (GASS) panel of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) "Global Energy and Water Exchanges" (GEWEX) project¹¹. As a submission to the competition, we ask for a single plot, accompanied by a page describing the analysis and the result. We specifically encourage early career scientists and scientists from developing countries to submit their analysis. ESiWACE supports this competition by hosting simulation data at DKRZ and by serving as an analysis hub. In corporation with GEWEX and the Department Of Energy Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (DOE-ARM), ESiWACE will also provide travel grants for the winners of the data analysis competition.

We are currently planning a virtual seminar series featuring the datasets of the DYAMOND Winter inter-comparison. This is inspired by the Single Model Initial Condition Large Ensemble (SMILE) webinar series¹² and the DKRZ Tech Talks¹³.

At EGU 2021, a session titled High resolution modelling of weather and climate¹⁴ will have a special focus on the DYAMOND intercomparison and will help highlighting this project.

We had planned to inform about this activity at an ESiWACE/DKRZ booth at EGU 2020, but this fell victim to COVID-19.

We are asking researchers using the datasets to acknowledge ESiWACE¹⁵. We expect this and word of mouth to be extremely effective in spreading the word in the global community of high resolution modellers.

¹¹<https://www.gewex.org/panels/global-atmospheric-system-studies-panel/>

¹²<https://large-ensemble.github.io/webinars/archive/>

¹³<https://www.dkrz.de/p/tech-talks>

¹⁴<https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/session/40829>

¹⁵<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/dyiamond/acknowledging-esiwace-and-dkrz>

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

See table 1.

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

Dueben, Peter D., Nils P. Wedi, Sami Saarinen, Christian Zeman, (2020). Global Simulations of the Atmosphere at 1.45 km Grid-Spacing with the Integrated Forecasting System, Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II, Volume 98, Issue 3, Pages 551-572, Online ISSN 2186-9057, Print ISSN 0026-1165, <https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2020-016>

Wedi, Nils P., Inna Polichtchouk, Peter D. Dueben, Valentine G. Anantharaj, Peter Bauer, Souhall Boussetta, et al. 2020. A baseline for global weather and climate simulations at 1 km resolution. Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems, Volume 12, Pages e2020MS002192. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020MS002192>

Judt, Falko, Daniel Klocke, Rosimar Rios-Berrios, Benoit Vanniere, Florian Ziemer, et al. Tropical Cyclones in Global, Storm-Resolving Models, Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan, **(in review)**

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None.

Table 1: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Conference Session	EGU 2021 Session High resolution modelling of weather and climate	19-30 April 2021	Scientists	https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/session/40829	(tbd)
Competition	GEWEX GASS competition	GEWEX Newsletter in preparation	Scientists		

Appendices

A README file of the DYAMOND Data library

```
#——  
#  
# Welcome to the DYAMOND data set library  
#  
#——
```

This directory is structured as follows:

- * indices/ – this folder contains the list of indices of the data archived in DKRZ's HPSS tape archive
- * requests/ – in this folder, requests for data can be made
- * data/ – DYAMOND data sets according to the latest data requests
- * scripts/ – here you can find some example post-processing scripts

Since the DYAMOND data sets contain hundreds of terabytes of data, most of the data is archived in DKRZ's HPSS tape archive. To access the data sets associated with the project, you will need to make a request. The ESiWACE team at DKRZ will download the data for you to the project folder data/, thereby making it accessible to all DYAMOND users. Since the data sets will be read-only, you will have to define the respective subfolder as the source directory for your post-processing scripts in your home/ or scratch/ folder. In order not to blow up the amount of memory used in this project, unused data sets will be deleted from the project folder on a regular basis

For any questions, contact us via esiwace.dyamond@dkrz.de

How to access DYAMOND data?

To search for a data set:

Use the listems tool, which is part of the packems module. Further information about packems and listems can be found at:

<https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/esmenv/wiki/Packems#Unpackems> and
<https://pad.gwdg.de/s/SyPRpLH.w#>

– load the module file
\$ module add packems

– renew your kerberos ticket
\$ tapeinit

If you do not have access to the tape library without entering a password please follow the recommended procedure described at:

<https://www.dkrz.de/up/systems/hpss/pftp-with-kerberos>.

– search for your files

e.g.: for a file named "nwp_R2B08_lkm1012_atm_3d_w_ml_20160909T*" within the archive index "ICON-10km" (the awk command is for better readability of the result)

```
$ listems -i indices/summer_data/ICON-10km '
nwp_R2B08_lkm1012_atm_3d_w_ml_20160909T*' | awk {'print $1" \t"$2'}
```

If your desired model does not have its own archive index file, you can search in the full index list full_index

e.g.: searching for a file named "v200_C3072_144x72.fre.nc" contained in a tarball named "*FV3-3.25km*" (the awk command is for a better readability of the result)

```
$ listems -l indices/summer_data/full_index 'v200_C3072_144x72.fre.nc' -a
'*FV3-3.25km*' | awk {'print $1" \t"$2'}
```

To request a data set:

- Write a file in the requests/ folder named: request_<YOUR.ID>
List here your desired tarballs with their paths, as given in the archive indices or by listems. An example request can be found in requests/example_request_k555555
- The content of this folder will be delivered to the ESIWACE project office by e-mail every night. We will then download this data for you to the folder data/, where it will be accessible (read-only) to all DYAMOND users.
- In your post-processing script, you can access the data by defining the subfolder as a source directory,
e.g.: \$ DATA_SOURCE_DIR='/work/bk1040/DYAMOND/data/ICON-10km'